

Seed protein (% of initial line)

Total seed protein production of rice mutants. Haryana, India.

higher grain yield and whose fineness matches that of Basmati 370 have been developed. A recombinant with superfine grain is being tested. Two early, fine-grained, higher yielding mutants of IR8 also have been obtained.

Seed protein production of all these mutants is much higher than that of their corresponding initial lines (see figure). The mutants have been tested for performance, stability, and adaptability for four generations. ■

Improvement of local rice varieties by pureline selection in Afghanistan

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Rice is the third most important cereal crop in Afghanistan, covering 2 10,000 hectares, 16.6% of the total cropped area. Rice cultivation is concentrated in two zones — Nangarhar in the East with 34% and Baghlan in the North with 43% of the total rice area.

Almost all the rice area is planted to indigenous varieties of high quality with long slender translucent grains, but they seem badly mixed. Local varieties are tall growing with weak stems and are prone to lodging. They respond poorly to fertilization, with the result that the average rice yield is stabilized at about 2 t/ha.

The important, good quality commercial rice varieties are Barah, Mahin, Lawangin, Basmati, and Dehraduni.

Performance of promising strains developed by pureline selection from local varieties at the Sheesham Bagh Agricultural Research Station, Jalalabad.

Commercial variety	Strain no.	Av yield (t/ha) 1975-78	Increase over bulk	
			kg/ha	%
Barah	5	3.3	801	31.5
	12	3.0	436	17.2
	Bulk	2.5	—	—
Mahin	2	2.8	68	2.5
	15	2.8	65	2.4
	27	3.1	311	11.3
	Bulk	2.8	—	—
Lawangin	11	3.1	549	17.7
	16	3.5	438	14.1
	Bulk	3.1	—	—
Basmati	3	2.9	32	1.1
	6	3.5	692	23.8
	Bulk	2.9	—	—
Dehraduni	8	2.5	357	16.5
	12	3.0	826	38.1
	21	3.5	1311	60.5
	Bulk	2.2	—	—

They have been grown since time immemorial without attempts to bring about varietal improvement. Each variety is a mixture of a number of morphologically similar lines. Systematic pureline selection work was initiated in 1972 at the Sheesham Bagh Agricultural Research Station, Jalalabad, Nangarhar.

Single plant progenies were compared with bulk varieties. Pure breeding and promising strains were further tested in 2-4 year replicated varietal trials 1975-

1978. Two to three best quality and yield strains have been selected in each variety.

The new strains yielded an average 32 kg/ha (1.12%) to 1311 kg/ha (60.51%) more than their respective bulk varieties (see table). Strains No. 5 in Barah, No. 27 in Mahin, No. 11 in Lawangin, No. 6 in Basmati, and No. 21 in Dehraduni have been selected for further multiplication to replace local commercial varieties. ■

Performance of direct-sown photo-period-sensitive rices at varying nitrogen levels under shallow-deep water at North Bihar, India

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A field trial during the 1980 wet season at the Rajendra Agricultural University Farm, Pusa, was laid out in a split plot design with three replications. Three nitrogen levels (0, 20, and 40 kg/ha) were assigned to main plots and 7 varieties (64-117, 62-68, 62-31, 62-10, BR14, Parwapankh, and Akalbir) were assigned to subplots. Soil type was clay loam with 0.7% organic carbon, 11.2 kg available P₂O₅/ha, and 208 kg available K₂O/ha. The pH was 8.4 and the EC 0.35 mmho/cm.

Seeds were drilled 21 May in rows 20 cm apart, at a rate of 80 kg seed/ha. After weeding the first week of July, nitrogen through urea was applied as top-dressing. Rainwater from catchments started accumulating the last week of July and maximum water depth went to 81 cm in late August. Harvest was in early December.

64-117 and Parwapankh had significantly higher yields than other varieties (see table). High yields were due to more panicles and a higher grain weight (resulting in heavier panicles) in 64-117, and a higher number of spikelets per panicle and higher spikelet fertility in Parwapankh. Maximum plant height was recorded in Akalbir, indicating it may be suitable for medium-deepwater areas.

Neither grain yield nor any other plant characteristics were influenced sig-